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THE HIDDEN PRICE OF COMPRESSED TEACHING IN FRACTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Fractions are among the most challenging topics for elementary learners, and the difficulty often increases due to limited instructional time and strict curriculum pacing. This study examined how Grades 3 to 6 mathematics teachers in public elementary schools in Abuyog, Leyte perceive the effects of time constraints on teaching fractions. Using a quantitative descriptive-comparative design, data were collected from 30 purposively selected teachers through a validated Likert-scale questionnaire. Findings revealed that teachers frequently experience time pressure, classroom disruptions, and rigid pacing that force them to rush or skip lessons. No significant differences were found based on age, gender, years of service, or designation. The results indicate that institutional factors such as curriculum rigidity, mass promotion, and administrative tasks, rather than teacher characteristics, contribute to instructional challenges. The study concludes that limited instructional time weakens mastery learning and recommends flexible pacing, mastery-based instruction, reduced non-teaching workloads, and supportive policies to strengthen students' understanding of fractions.

Keywords: instructional time, curriculum pacing, teacher perceptions, fractions, elementary mathematics, student performance, mass promotion, teaching practices, Abuyog Leyte

INTRODUCTION

The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) continues to show that many students struggle with mathematical literacy, especially in foundational skills such as fractions, decimals, and percentages. In the 2022 results, a large number of students performed at the lowest proficiency levels, reflecting persistent gaps in understanding (OECD, 2023). This issue is not only global but also evident in the Philippines, where studies by Bermejo and Vistro-Yu (2023) confirm that Filipino learners continue to face significant misconceptions in learning fractions.

These gaps are often tied to how teachers manage instructional time. Pressured by curriculum demands, administrative tasks, and class suspensions, many are forced to rush or omit lessons. Fractions, being both foundational and abstract, require consistent scaffolding and practice elements that are lost when time is misused. The Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2024) reported that non-teaching duties and disruptions further reduce effective teaching time, especially in mathematics.

Research underscores the value of sufficient, quality instruction. Kraft and Novicoff (2024) emphasized that the structure and duration of instructional time foster deeper understanding, while Ismail, Maat, and Khalid (2024) highlighted that teachers' pacing decisions directly affect students' mastery of fractions. Education Week (2024) echoed this, warning that fragmented fraction instruction leaves long-term comprehension gaps.

This study therefore examines how the skipping or compression of lessons in fractions affects Grade 3–6 learners' performance. It aligns with DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, which emphasizes structured instruction. Findings aim to guide teachers, administrators, and policymakers in ensuring sufficient time for foundational topics, improving teaching practices, and building stronger mathematical foundations for students.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching fractions is a crucial yet challenging part of elementary mathematics. Specifically, this study examines how time constraints, disruptions, curriculum pacing, and teacher beliefs influence instructional decisions and skipped lessons in teaching fractions:

1. What is the profile of the mathematics teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Length of Service
 - 1.4 Teacher's Designation
2. What are the perceptions of mathematics teachers regarding the hidden price of compressed teaching in fractions in terms of:
 - 2.1 Perceived Instructional Time Pressure during the Teaching of Fractions (INDICATOR 1)
 - 2.2 Instructional Adjustments due to Disruptions and Curriculum Demands (INDICATOR 2)
 - 2.3 Teacher Decision-Making Influenced by Assumptions about Student Progression (INDICATOR 3)
 - 2.4 Curriculum Expectations and Pacing Adjustments by Teachers (INDICATOR 4)
 - 2.5 Beliefs about Fraction Learning across Grade Levels (INDICATOR 5)
3. Is there a significant difference in the hidden price of compressed teaching in fractions based on the teachers' profiles?
4. What general wellness program can be developed to address the instructional challenges faced by teachers in Abuyog, Leyte?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-comparative design under a quantitative action research approach to determine teachers' profiles and perceptions and identify significant differences based on age, gender, length of service, and designation.

Research Instrument

Data were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire with two parts: demographic profile and five indicators time pressure, disruptions, decision-making, curriculum pacing, and beliefs on fraction learning. Expert-validated, pilot-tested, and checked through Cronbach's Alpha, the instrument proved reliable for data collection.

Validation of the Research Instrument

The researcher-made questionnaire underwent content and construct validation by three experts in mathematics education and research to ensure clarity and relevance. After minor revisions and a pilot test, Cronbach's Alpha confirmed the instrument's validity and reliability for data collection.

Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted in selected public elementary schools in Abuyog, Leyte. Schools were chosen for varied sizes and settings to obtain authentic insights from mathematics teachers with direct experience in teaching fractions.

Participant Selection and Sampling

The study involved 30 purposively selected elementary mathematics teachers from Abuyog, Leyte, meeting criteria of teaching mathematics, handling fractions in the past year, and willingness to participate. Conducted from June to August 2025, it gathered insights on skipped or compressed lessons.

Data Gathering Procedure

School approval was secured before distributing questionnaires. Participants were informed of the study's purpose, ensured confidentiality, gave consent, and their responses were collected, encoded, and analyzed for academic purposes.

Statistical Treatment

Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation) summarized the data, while inferential analyses using t-tests and ANOVA examined perception differences across teacher profiles. Results were presented in tables and figures with direct interpretations aligned to research questions.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards: participation was voluntary with the right to withdraw anytime, ensuring confidentiality, anonymity, and secure data handling. Permission from school administrators was obtained, and teacher duties were respected to prevent work disruptions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of data from Grades 3–6 mathematics teachers in Abuyog, Leyte, focusing on instructional decisions in teaching fractions. Findings are organized by research problems, with data summarized through frequencies, percentages, means, and ANOVA results, supported by narrative interpretation.

1. What is the profile of the mathematics teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Length of Service
 - 1.4 Teacher's Designation

Table 1.1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
55 – 65	5	16.67%
45 – 54	8	26.67%
35 – 44	11	36.67%
26 – 34	6	20%
Below 25 years old	0	0
TOTAL	30	100%

Table 1.1 shows that most teacher-respondents are aged 35–44 (36.67%), followed by 45–54 (26.67%) and 26–34 (20%), indicating a predominantly mid- to senior-level teaching workforce.

Table 1.2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MALE	7	23.33%
FEMALE	23	76.67%
TOTAL	30	100%

The gender distribution of teacher respondents from Abuyog, Leyte reveals that 76.67% of teacher respondents are female and 23.33% are male, indicating a female-dominated teaching workforce.

Table 1.3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

LENGTH OF SERVICE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1 - 4	3	10%
5 - 8	6	20%
9 - 12	4	13.33%
13 - 16	7	23.33%
17 and above	10	33.33%
TOTAL	30	100%

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Data show that most teacher-respondents have 17+ years of service (33.33%), followed by 13–16 years (23.33%), indicating a highly experienced teaching workforce.

Table 1.4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Teacher's Designation

DESIGNATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Teacher I	3	10%
Teacher II	4	13.33%
Teacher III	16	53.33%
Master Teacher I	5	16.67
Master Teacher II	2	6.67%
Master Teacher III	0	0
TOTAL	30	100%

Table 1.4 shows most respondents are Teacher III (53.33%), followed by Master Teacher I (16.67%), indicating a highly experienced teaching workforce.

2. What are the perceptions of math teachers regarding the hidden price of compressed teaching in fractions in terms of

- 2.1 Perceived Instructional Time Pressure During the Teaching of Fractions (INDICATOR 1)
- 2.2 Instructional Adjustments Due to Disruptions and Curriculum Demands (INDICATOR 2)
- 2.3 Teacher Decision-Making Influenced by Assumptions About Student Progression (INDICATOR 3)
- 2.4 Curriculum Expectations and Pacing Adjustments by Teachers (INDICATOR 4)
- 2.5 Beliefs About Fraction Learning Across Grade Levels (INDICATOR 5)

Legend:

SCALE	RANGE	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51-3.24	Agree
2	1.75-2.50	Disagree
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree

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Table 2.1

Perceived Instructional Time Pressure During the Teaching of Fractions (INDICATOR 1)	MEAN	VI
1. I often feel rushed when teaching math due to limited instructional time.	2.6	Agree
2. I find it difficult to give students enough practice due to time constraints.	2.53	Agree
3. I reduce class discussions to stay on schedule with the curriculum.	2.83	Agree
4. I feel that my fraction lessons are affected by strict time limits.	2.53	Agree
5. I rarely have time to review or reteach topics in the allotted time.	2.9	Agree
6. I sometimes have to skip examples or activities because of pacing deadlines.	2.50	Agree
7. I believe that more instructional time would improve how I teach fractions.	2.63	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.65	Agree

Table 2.2

Instructional Adjustments Due to Disruptions and Curriculum Demands (INDICATOR 2)	MEAN	VI
1. Unplanned activities often interrupt my math instruction schedule.	2.53	Agree
2. Administrative meetings or school events take time away from teaching.	2.5	Agree
3. I have to rush my lessons after losing time to disruptions.	2.63	Agree
4. Unexpected schedule changes prevent me from completing some lessons.	2.5	Agree
5. School-level decisions sometimes reduce the number of teaching days.	2.53	Agree
6. I adjust my lesson plans frequently due to external	2.50	Agree

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interruptions.		
7. Disruptions significantly affect the coverage of me fraction lessons.	2.53	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.53	Agree

Table 2.3

Teacher Decision-Making Influenced by Assumptions About Student Progression (INDICATOR 3)	MEAN	VI
1. I feel less pressure to complete all topics because most students are promoted.	2.70	Agree
2. Even if students struggle, I continue moving through the lessons because they will pass.	2.87	Agree
3. Mass promotion affects my motivation to ensure mastery of all topics.	2.60	Agree
4. I sometimes think it's unnecessary to stress over content mastery due to promotion policies.	2.70	Agree
5. I feel that effort is undervalued since all students pass anyway.	2.67	Agree
6. The current promotion policy influences how I plan my lessons.	2.57	Agree
7. I do not focus much on assessments since they don't affect student promotion.	2.97	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.72	Agree

Table 2.4

Curriculum Expectations and Pacing Adjustments by Teachers (INDICATOR 4)	MEAN	VI
1. The pacing guide moves too quickly for my students to fully understand fractions.	2.5	Agree
2. I compress lessons to keep up with the required timeline.	2.67	Agree
3. I find the curriculum unrealistic in terms of time and student capacity.	2.67	Agree

4. I am expected to follow a curriculum pace even when students struggle.	2.53	Agree
5. I feel forced to choose speed over depth in teaching.	3.10	Agree
6. The pacing guide limits my flexibility in adapting lessons.	2.70	Agree
7. Curriculum expectations create pressure that affects teaching quality.	2.80	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.71	Agree

Table 2.5.

Beliefs About Fraction Learning Across Grade Levels (INDICATOR 5)	MEAN	VI
1. I skip some lessons knowing that students will encounter them again in higher grades.	2.97	Agree
2. I believe it's acceptable to focus on easier topics and leave harder ones for later grades.	3.00	Agree
3. I rely on the assumption that upper grade teachers will reinforce topics I skip.	3.07	Agree
4. I avoid repeating topics if they will be covered again in later years.	3.03	Agree
5. Some fraction lessons are not urgent because they are revisited in higher grades.	3.07	Agree
6. It's better to briefly introduce a topic now and let future teachers expand on it.	3.00	Agree
7. I see early grade instruction in fractions as more about exposure than mastery.	2.73	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.98	Agree

3. Is there a significant difference in the hidden price of compressed teaching in fractions based on their profiles?

Table 3.1. Significant difference of The Hidden Price of Compressed Teaching in Fractions according to Age

VARIABLE	F-VALUE	SIG.	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
INDICATOR 1	2.605	.073	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 2	1.657	.201	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 3	.548	.654	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 4	.272	.845	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 5	.555	.649	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 3.2. Significant difference of The Hidden Price of Compressed Teaching in Fractions according to Gender

VARIABLE	F-VALUE	SIG.	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
INDICATOR 1	1.587	.218	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 2	.496	.487	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 3	.005	.942	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 4	.792	.381	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 5	.286	.597	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 3.3. Significant difference of The Hidden Price of Compressed Teaching in Fractions according to Length of Service

VARIABLE	F-VALUE	SIG.	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
INDICATOR 1	2.062	.116	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 2	1.516	.228	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 3	1.938	.135	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 4	.648	.633	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 5	1.225	.325	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 3.4. Significant difference of The Hidden Price of Compressed Teaching in Fractions according to Teacher's Designation

VARIABLE	F-VALUE	SIG.	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
INDICATOR 1	.721	.585	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 2	.687	.607	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 3	.897	.481	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 4	2.566	.063	Accept H_0	Not Significant
INDICATOR 5	.274	.892	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Teaching fractions is one of the most challenging areas in elementary mathematics. However, the results of this study revealed that teachers often face insufficient instructional time, which leads them to skip or compress lessons. This chapter presents the summary of findings, the conclusions drawn from the results, and the recommendations for improving instructional practices and curriculum implementation.

Summary of Findings

This study examined the practices of elementary mathematics teachers in Abuyog, Leyte, from Grades 3 to 6 in relation to time constraints, skipped lessons, and compromises to student learning in fractions. Based on the statement of the problem, the following findings were drawn:

1. Profile of the mathematics teacher-respondents

Most math teachers were females aged 35–44 with over 17 years of experience, mainly Teacher III, all facing similar challenges in managing limited teaching time.

2. Perceptions of mathematics teachers regarding the hidden price of compressed teaching in fractions:

2.1 Perceived Instructional Time Pressure

Over half of the teachers (62.3%) felt pressured by the curriculum timeframe, leading them to skip or shorten fraction lessons to keep up, despite students' struggles to follow.

2.2 Instructional Adjustments due to Disruptions and Curriculum Demands

About 63% of teachers said school activities and disruptions reduced teaching time, forcing them to skip or shorten lessons to meet curriculum requirements despite students' difficulties.

2.3 Teacher Decision-Making Influenced by Assumptions about Student Progression

Most teachers (68%) said the mass promotion policy led them to skip lessons, as students advance without mastery, causing learning gaps despite their awareness of its effects.

2.4 Curriculum Expectations and Pacing Adjustments by Teachers

Most teachers (68%) said the curriculum moved too fast, giving little time for deep teaching, forcing them to rush or skip fraction topics.

2.5 Beliefs about Fraction Learning across Grade Levels

Most teachers (75%) believed fractions would be retaught in higher grades, leading them to skip or shorten lessons, assuming students would learn them later.

3. Difference in the hidden price of compressed teaching in fractions based on teachers' profiles

The study found that age, gender, experience, and position did not affect teaching practices. All teachers faced time pressure, often forcing them to skip or shorten lessons to keep up with the curriculum.

Conclusions

The study concludes that teaching difficulties in fractions arise from systemic issues, not teacher incompetence. Rigid pacing, tight schedules, and mass promotion force teachers to rush or skip lessons, resulting in shallow understanding and weak student foundations.

The scripted curriculum restricts flexibility, while excessive paperwork and non-academic tasks reduce teaching time and shift focus from learning to compliance. These pressures make mastery and honest reporting difficult. The problem lies within the education system, not individual teachers.

Reforms must prioritize depth over speed, protect instructional time, and support teacher integrity. The Department of Education should ensure policies that promote mastery-based learning and realistic pacing to improve instructional quality and student understanding.

Recommendations

The findings reveal that skipped lessons and shallow learning are systemic issues needing collective action. Teachers should apply adaptive pacing and mastery-based approaches, while administrators must promote instructional flexibility and reduce disruptions. The Department of Education should align the curriculum with realistic teaching time, discourage mass promotion, and emphasize authentic learning. Students must engage actively and practice consistently. Future researchers should further examine time, pacing, and workload effects. Altogether, these actions call for systemic reforms that prioritize mastery, integrity, and genuine learning.

References

- Bermejo, J. L., & Vistro-Yu, C. P. (2023). "It's not just the language": Grade 4 pupils' understanding of fractions. *The Mathematician Educator*, 4(1), 23–54. <https://ame.org.sg/2023/06/15/tme2023-vol-4-no-1-pp-23-54>
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2015). DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015: Policy guidelines on classroom assessment for the K to 12 basic education program. Department of Education, Philippines. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/04/01/do-8-s-2015-policy-guidelines-on-classroom-assessment-for-the-k-to-12-basic-education-program>
- Education Week. (2024, October 7). Fractions are tough to teach and to

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learn; these strategies can help. Education Week. <https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/fractions-are-tough-to-teach-and-to-learn-these-strategies-can-help/2024/10>

Ismail, S. A., et al. (2024). Understanding the challenges and strategies in teaching fractions: Insights from experienced mathematics teachers. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v13-i3/20345>

Kraft, M. A., & Novicoff, S. (2024). Time in school: A conceptual framework, synthesis of causal research, and empirical exploration. *American Educational Research Journal*, 61(4), 724–766. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312241251857>

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). PISA 2022 results (Volume I): The state of learning and equity in education. OECD Publishing. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/pisa-2022-results-volume-i_53f23881-en.html

Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS). (2024, February 29). 53 teaching days lost in SY 2023–2024. <https://www.pids.gov.ph/details/news/in-the-news/53-teaching-days-lost-in-sy-2023-2024-edcom-2-pids>

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